

Style for *IRRN* Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*; Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double-spaced. ¶

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

RxT-42 or Himdhan, a new, stable, high yielding rice for hilly areas of Himachal Pradesh, India

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Himachal Pradesh (H.P.) is a hilly state with undulating topography and diverse agroclimate conditions that range from subtropical to temperate. In the kharif season, rice is an important crop. It occupies 100,000 ha and is cultivated at altitudes as high as 2,290 m.

Many rice varieties are needed for H.P.'s diverse agroclimatic conditions. Most recommended varieties – including IR579, the recently recommended high yielding variety with good grain quality – are suitable for areas up to 1,070 m. Norin 18 and Norin 8, japonica types recommended for high-altitude areas between 915 and 1,370 m, are not popular with farmers because of their coarse grain and poor cooking quality. China 988 with medium-coarse grain is the only variety that can be cultivated from the plains up to an altitude of 1,525 m. It is the most widely grown recommended variety, but it is susceptible to blast disease and lodging, and needs to be replaced.

The experimental line RxT-42 consistently performed well and outyielded China 988, Norin 18, and IR579 in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) and H. P. University trials from 1970–76. Its overall yield, based on 25 AICRIP trials, was 4.1 t/ha, an increase of about 13% over that for China 988 (3.6 t/ha) (see table). In yearly trials, RxT-42 outyielded China 988 by 5.4 to 28.4%.

Yield stability parameters for 20 rices tested in the Elite Varieties Trials (EVT) during 1975 and 1976 in 14 environments, at elevations ranging from 308 to 1,371 m, indicated that RxT-42

Overall mean yield of RxT-42 and China 988 from 1970 to 1976. Himachal Pradesh, India.

Year	No. of locations	Average yield (t/ha)	
		RxT-42	China 988
1910	1	6.3	4.9
1911	5	5.1	4.2
1912	2	4.2	3.9
1913	10	5.1	4.3
1914	1	4.1	3.1
1915	10	3.6	3.4
1916	33	3.1	3.4
Mean		4.1	3.6

had average performance (mean yield, 2.4 kg per 2 × 3-m plot) and high stability (regression, 0.87 and deviation from regression, 0.016). It yielded significantly higher than China 988.

RxT-42 can easily replace China 988 at elevations of up to 1,370 m in H.P. and other hilly areas of India, and has recently been recommended to the State Variety Release Committee for release under the name Himdhan. The AICRIP Annual Workshop also recommended it for release in H.P. in April 1977.

RxT-42 is a progeny of the cross R-575/TN1. R-575 is a purple-leaved, tall, stiff-strawed, and blast-resistant local recommended variety. RxT-42 matures only 2 to 4 days later than China 988 and has more spikelets per panicle and higher test weight. ¶

Breeding methods used in 10 Asian nations

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As part of an IRRI study of rice breeding programs in Asia, a survey was made of the breeding methods used in hybridization programs by 31 rice breeders at 24 research centers in 10 Asian countries. The project, initiated in 1975, was partially funded by a research grant from the Rockefeller Foundation.